

Creative Writing as an Effective Method of Learning English as a Foreign Language: A case study of Arab learners

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Introduction

Teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) in the Arab world countries encounters critical challenges. Different departments of English in those countries fail to meet the expectations of improving the written and spoken English of their students (Fareh, 2010). This condition calls for the need to spend more efforts in the attempt to determine the causes and solutions of the problem. Scholars of TEFL have identified several reasons. Abukhattala (2013) points out that the teacher's traditional role in the classroom in the Arab world countries is the main problem. Cooperative learning and student-centered classrooms are essential activities required to achieve efficiency and contribute to the solution; however they are rarely effectively practiced in those conventional educational systems (Abukhattala, 2013). Teaching English as a foreign language in the Arab world should therefore adopt new innovative methods that pay enough attention to the cooperative role of the student and teacher in the classroom.

The traditional approaches to teaching English in the Arab world are more problematic when they are examined in the context of the departments of English language and literature at Arab countries' universities. These departments are expected to be the most effective environments where English is taught as a foreign language in those countries. Most learners of English apart from those in these departments learn it for pragmatic reasons that give them a passion to acquire the language. This passion is most probably absent in the academic domains of higher education where the students learn English as an academic discipline. Introducing new attractive methods of teaching English is highly valuable in this situation. The integration of teaching language and literature in one class can be a useful and attainable method in this regard. The departments of English language and literature can achieve this through adding a creative writing course to the curriculum of the English undergraduate programme. Creative writing can be both an influential and effective English learning tool for its ability to prompt the students to adequately participate in the class activities, enjoyably use the language, and in the process, improve it.

Rationale

Teaching English as a foreign language for undergraduate Arab learners in departments of English language and literature encounters different obstacles all of which relate to the level of mastery of the language they can achieve. The majority of the students in these departments are often not exposed before university to appropriate environments where English is purely used as a medium of communication either as speakers or listeners. The pre-university educational system of learning English as a foreign language at schools in the Arab world usually fails to equip the learners with the skills needed to master the language; it offers English as a subject needed for examination purposes rather than competencies to be acquired (Al-Issa, Al-Bulushi, & Al-Zadjali, 2017). It is urgent therefore to take practical steps to deal with the learning challenges encountered by learners of English as a foreign language at university departments of English language and literature in the Arab world.

Another view of the scholarship on TEFL in the Arab world shows that two approaches have been used by scholars. The first approach places great emphasis on identifying the problems the learners of English as a foreign language encounter, and pays less attention to the creative treatment of them. Fareh (2010), Abukhattala (2013), Al-Issa, *et al.* (2017) and Jiménez (2015) fall within this group. Jiménez (2015) focuses on three main factors that affect language competence of learners of English as a foreign language, which are: 1- the students' lack of motivation, 2- problems related to the learning environment and 3- mother tongue interference. These factors, among others mentioned above, form part of the challenge encountered by learners of English as a foreign language in the Arab world, and the method proposed in this study will be examined with regard to them.

The second approach, which this study can reasonably be classified within, has for its main objective the invention of creative methods to implement in TEFL classrooms intended to address the problems that face Arab learners of English. Identifying these problems is essential to develop the most effective method. The above argument has diagnosed challenges represented in the traditional

methods of instruction, the lack of motivation, the learning environment and the mother tongue impact on the learner; however a close view of some classroom activities in Arab world universities is still needed to determine the efficiency of proposed solutions.

EFL learners at departments of English language and literature need to deal with courses other than language skills such as literature, linguistics and translation. Studying these courses with insufficient English language competence would notably impact on their learning. The teaching faculty needs to develop an appropriate awareness of the main reasons related to the educational environment causing this problem. One critical reason is indoctrination, or the 'banking method' of education, which is used in some learning contexts. The learning process in this condition depends mostly on unproductive memorization of the studied material instead of analyzing it which would better benefit the learner. The outcome of this method is the same as constructing a building on the surface with no foundation, hence it is vulnerable. The instruction received by the learners as a result does not positively improve their acquired language.

EFL learners tend to be concerned with the question of having the ability to control a listening session or a conversation. These concerns can be the result of some of the reasons mentioned above; however they can often be also related to difficulties of obtaining the syntactic skills required to use the English sentence communicatively. This could be attributed to the dominant employment of outdated methods like Grammar-Translation in teaching EFL in some Arab countries (Yaseen, Ismail, & Yasin, 2018). Teaching English grammar for Arab students in various schools and universities in Jordan for instance is based on their ability to memorize particular rules and key-words rather than to communicate language effectively. This aborts the efforts to help the learners to master the use of English. This approach to English teaching turns the language into a lifeless tool, and distracts the learners' mental interaction from communicating ideas to fall into futile attempts to recognize tenses or parts of speech.

The demand to develop innovative, non-mechanical, models of teaching English as a foreign language by EFL scholars who are exposed to those challenges and deal with the above problems is consequently urgent. The curricula of the undergraduate programmes of English language and literature in Jordan for instance often pay little attention to this claim. They mostly include language skills, literature, linguistics, translation and research courses. The language skills courses alone cannot help solve EFL learning problems without the inclusion of the other courses in the curriculum. Some course akin to a content and language integrated learning approach (CLIL) is needed. This research consequently proposes a solution to this by recommending the inclusion of a

creative writing course in the curriculum of English language and literature. The value of similar courses lies in the significant writing and reading training activities they can add to the process of learning. To make this process more exciting, thus more valuable and instructive, it is advised that the creative writing courses focus on the reading and writing of poetry; for the composition of poetry relies on an intensive use of imaginative language that renders the learning process enjoyable. It is against this background that this study proposes a creative writing course of poetry as an effective interactive tool for solving the problems of EFL learning in this research context.

Discussion

Poetry's oral tradition and EFL learning

Poetry has been endeared to the human mind since classical antiquity. It was the sole literary type used by authors of ancient Greece and Rome, thus can be regarded as 'the mother of all literature'. The choice of poetry as a literary form appropriate for the artistic condition of the ancients is basically related to the quality of memorization – that poetry is easy to memorize and recite. This feature positioned poetry within the tradition of oral storytelling in ancient times. The memorization of poetry is evidently a pleasant experience for the musical qualities it possesses. Its recitation is hardly less exciting as it involves musicality exposure of feelings, thoughts, experiences and/or events. But how is all that instrumental in the process of EFL learning?

One of the problems encountered by EFL learners is the acquisition of enough English words, terms and expressions. These are necessary for the different linguistic interactions such as listening comprehension, establishing a good conversation, reading an article or writing about any subject. The memorizability of poetry is ultimately a productive quality compared with the above mentioned unproductive memorization of rules and key-words, because poetry is both a rich source of vocabulary and of syntactic structures which the learner of EFL can employ for language interactions. Munden (2015) argues that poetry engages the teachers and their students 'by the fundamental connection between poetry and the memory' (p.68). The teaching of poetry as a creative writing form in this context is substantially useful as it becomes a rich source of language that nourishes the memory of the EFL learner. However it needs to be regulated so as to achieve the maximum desired benefit. Two interactive approaches to poetry as a creative writing form are examined in this regard. The first relies on the concept of entertainment and provocativeness resulted from reading and rewriting poetry; it employs haiku poetry for its application. The second centres on stimulating the learners to reproduce particular poems through applying a cento poetry

activity that relies on creating a new poem out of lines taken from different selected poems the learner chooses.

The attraction of reading and writing haiku poetry for EFL Learners

This section proposes an entertaining approach to EFL learning based on the delight reading and writing poetry brings. It centres on selecting short appealing poems capable of catching the attention of the average EFL learner. Haiku poetry can perfectly serve this purpose because its brevity makes it 'at once demanding and not quite overwhelming in its challenges' (Higginson & Harter 2009, p.47). Haiku is reliable for EFL learning as it helps to avoid the learners dealing with long passages that would distract their attention. Haiku poetry can also help the EFL learners 'to write fluently and acquire vocabulary because its form requires close attention to select the appropriate words to communicate specific feelings' (Iida, 2010, p.29). Haiku poetry can therefore create an exciting language learning challenge needed in the EFL classroom to creatively enrich the students' English vocabulary and methods of linguistic expression. It has the power to turn the interaction with English into a fully living tool of communication. Haiku can shift the process of learning English from being mundane into a lively attractive experience.

Application of haiku creative writing in an EFL classroom

The management of the EFL classroom to employ haiku poetry as a creative writing tool to learn English can follow different methods. An effective method in this respect centres on giving the EFL learners time to read a haiku poem of their choice from a group selected by the instructor. The initial aim is to pursue an understanding of the poem. Dictionaries can be used at this stage. The learners then have to put away the poems they have selected and begin the writing session. At this stage the learners have to write a haiku poem on their own that reflects the same meaning and situation of the former one depending on their faculty of productive memorization. Dictionaries should not be used at this stage. This activity is very effective in training the mind to recollect the memorized language, thus to permanently store it in the mind. The learners should reflect on particular features of the language such as the appropriateness of language use and choice of terms, the preciseness of reintroducing thought and the correctness of pronunciation. They next have to recite the haiku poems they have created aloud.

This activity can provide high levels of learning achievement if it is effectively implemented, for the following reasons. First it fulfills Sidney's notion that the aim of poetry is 'to teach and delight' (2002, p.86); poetry can be an outstanding medium for EFL learning as it teaches while it entertains the learner.

The EFL learner as a result can acquire new words and expressions, and make reasonable steps towards mastering the language in an easy, pleasant way. Secondly this approach helps the learners enrich their mental store with new English vocabulary as they need to keep particular keywords from the original haiku in their mind to be used in the later one they compose, and these particular words will practically remain in their long-term memory. Willmot (1973) in this regard argues that literature 'stimulates linguistic responses of various kinds. English teachers not only present literature; they also exploit it, because it can generate language as well as exemplify it' (p.57). Thirdly, this interactive method encourages the EFL learners to read their composition aloud, hence it offers them and the instructor an opportunity to evaluate their pronunciation, and train them to pronounce English words correctly under the instructor's supervision.

Application of haiku creative writing in an EFL classroom: Results

In a haiku creative EFL writing class in the above context of a Jordanian university EFL classroom, a group of students were given haiku poems and asked to select one and apply the above haiku activity to it. The results are given below. They display high levels of success in achieving the desired goals of employing the haiku creative writing activity in the EFL classroom. They reflect preciseness of reintroducing thought, correctness of language use, accurate selection of terms and appropriate use of language to convey thought. The following original poems and those re-produced by the learners demonstrate this, and highlight the usefulness of using haiku creative writing in the EFL learning process.

Learner	Original Haiku	Haiku Re-produced
1	Your sounds exploding in the universe return to earth in prayer	Outspreading your voice a passionate sound chanting into the prayers
2	Brighten up the day With memories and smile that's true When clock stops for thee	Brilliant aurora Astonishing! Ecstasy awaits but recollections
3	An afternoon breeze Expels cold air along with the fallen brown leaves	Autumn's comfort comes the refreshment of that breeze cold enough to feel

Cento composition to assist EFL learning

This section proposes another new approach to assist the EFL learning process through introducing a practical method of dealing with the courses of literature and creative writing in the undergraduate classes. The nature of the literary courses included in the curriculum is traditionally determined by the literary genres and epochs taught to the students aiming to create literary taste and knowledge. Studying these courses can indirectly help with matters of language improvement, but does not directly serve this purpose. A creative writing course where cento is taught can play a significant role in this regard. A cento is a poem made up of lines the student selects from different poems by one or more poets. Students consequently have to read several poems, understand selected favourite verses and then begin to write their own work. This section examines the advantages and ways of teaching cento as a creative writing course aiming to help improve the language proficiency of the EFL learners.

Implementation of a cento activity in EFL classrooms is noted for its effectiveness in providing successful language learning. In her article 'Writing Cento Poems in a Japanese EFL Classroom', Kamata (2019) investigates the merits of applying the cento teaching strategy in EFL learning environments. She states that while applying the cento activity in the EFL classroom:

The students would not be required to read and comprehend entire poems; they would only have to select favorite lines. Furthermore, those students who struggled to come up with original ideas on the spot would be spared the pressure of creating a poem from scratch. This exercise would also give them some practice in scanning texts for general meaning. (p.6)

Writing cento poetry can be therefore an effortless way to learn language. It helps to exclude the pressure exerted on the learner by the need to use particular vocabulary in writing a composition. It introduces the EFL learners to a world of terms and ideas already used in the original poem. All that they need is to build an understanding of their selected favorite lines, and then have them rearranged in a new fashion. This activity ultimately equips EFL learners with new ways of acquiring and using the language to help their needs.

Application of cento in a creative writing EFL classroom: Results

In the above context of a Jordanian university EFL classroom, the EFL learners in a cento creative writing class were requested to select poetry books that appeal to them most from a group of books the instructor prepared earlier. They were next required to begin selecting certain poems and particular verses from within them. They had finally to come up with a cento poem of at least four lines composed of mixing the various selected

lines together. The students' compositions were then read aloud by them and compared with each others'. This experience was enriching as the learners needed to build a good understanding of each line they chose so as to compose a cento that is linguistically correct and ideationally relevant. The samples below represent the products of this cento EFL classroom activity.

Learner 1

Verse	Sonnet	Line
I now have learned love right and learned even so	Astrophil 16	13
Far, far too long to learn it without book	Astrophil 56	2
And love I thought that I was full of thee	Astrophil 16	4
And all in war with time for love of you	Shakespeare 15	13
When my love swears that she is made of truth	Shakespeare 138	1
And yet, by heaven, I think my love is rare. (Variation)	Shakespeare 130	13

Learner 2

Verse	Sonnet	Line
Shall I compare thee to a summer's day?	Shakespeare 18	1
Me seemed I smelt a garden of sweet flowers.	Ammoretti 64	2
Which cupid's self from Beauty's mine did draw:	Astrophil 9	13
Of touch they are, and poor I am their straw.	Astrophil 9	14

Learner 3

Verse	Sonnet (Shakespeare)	Line
Love is not love	116	2
Which alters when it alteration finds	116	3
Love alters not with his brief hours and weeks,	116	11
O no! it is an ever-fixed mark,	116	5
Nay, if you read this line, remember not	71	5
The hand that writ it; for I love you so,	71	6
Holds in perfection but a little moment,	15	2
And yet it may be said I lov'd you so.	42	2

Conclusion

Creative writing courses possess a great academic value since they can be employed to support the process of EFL learning as this study has demonstrated through discussion and application. The study consequently proposes a reasonably constructive recommendation that a creative writing course is added to the curriculum of the English language and literature undergraduate programme in universities that teach English as a foreign language. Including such a course in the curricula has tremendous benefits. The EFL learners can enjoy practicing creative poetry writing as an effective classroom method that helps to avoid falling into the traps of the routine of traditional ways of instruction. Creative writing of poetry in EFL classrooms is an ever-renewing, profitable and enjoyable method of learning since poetry is an inexhaustible source of language.

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